

Co-creation activity #53 - Developing and promoting a cross-cutting and shared EOSC Glossary

Final report

Dario Mangione
dario.mangione@gmail.com

Abstract

The present report summarises the EOSC Secretariat.eu co-creation activity of developing and promoting the EOSC Glossary by stating its fundamentals and describing briefly its established processes, phases and results.

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Introduction

The necessity of a glossary pertinent to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) arises from the variety and specialisation of the possible viewpoints that can be adopted when trying to describe the aspects and define the concepts needed for the actual communication between the individuals and the organisations actively involved in shaping the foundations for the implementation of an open science and an open innovation paradigm in Europe.

The concurrence of many levels of specialisation and the different contexts of use requires the reconciliation at a common mediating level, the definition of a terminology based on the identification, the study and the analysis of the relevant concepts and the related terms. While many glossaries are publicly available, the simple recollection of terms and definitions is not in fact sufficient to provide alone the coherence that only a systematic approach can realise.

Such a glossary would be just the starting point for a standardisation process that can not be imposed on the communities, but must originate from them, based on a much needed discussion stemming from a collective validation phase.

The methodology used is in line with the standards ISO 704:2009 Terminology work — Principles and methods, ISO 860:2007 Terminology work — Harmonization of concepts and terms, ISO 1087:2019 Terminology work and terminology science — Vocabulary and ISO 10241-1:2011 Terminological entries in standards — Part 1: General requirements and examples of presentation.

Tasks and activities

The following are the identified tasks and related activities for this co-creation activity #53 - Developing and promoting a cross-cutting and shared EOSC Glossary:

1. the definition and establishment of the processes driving the development of the glossary, its monitoring and the validation of the results produced;
2. the analysis of official documents (literature, standards and EOSC relevant documents, including those released by the Commission and EOSC Experts Groups) in order to identify the concepts to be included in the glossary and their context of use;
3. the comparison and exploitation, whenever possible, of other relevant glossaries suggested by the Glossary Interest Group Community;
4. the development of appropriate definitions;
5. the moderation of the Glossary Interest Group Forum;
6. the organization of at least 3 Glossary IG meetings;
7. the amendment of glossary terms. The definition of glossary terms will be done in agreement with principles and methods specified by ISO 704:2009 (basis for the terminological definitions in standards ISO 10241 – 1:2011). This proposal is linked to the co-creation budget proposal “Supervising, monitoring and validating the development of the EOSC Glossary”. Three versions of the Glossary will be released respectively at M4, M7 and M10. Each release will be accompanied by a report describing the methodology used and the work done.

[1] The processes driving the development of the glossary, its monitoring and the validation of the results produced have been defined and established in line with the standards *ISO 704:2009 Terminology work — Principles and methods* and *ISO 10241-1:2011 Terminological entries in standards — Part 1: General requirements and examples of presentation* and have been mainly carried out through biweekly virtual meetings scheduled, from March 2020 to December 2020, with Leonardo Candela (but also through chats and emails whenever believed necessary) and the use of shared documents supporting real-time collaborative editing, which has been instrumental for enabling contributions from the available and willing parties.

Since the beginning of the work, thanks to the Glossary Interest Group facilitator and the supervisor, contacts were made with the Working Groups and the possible interested parties in order to establish an initial list of the most relevant terms to work on and to enquire about the terminologies and glossaries already developed and analogous projects or initiatives.

A preliminary analysis based on the *EOSC main background documents* (see [Appendix A](#)) provided the basis for a first assessment of the target groups of the glossary and of its domains of interest.

A first analysis of the concepts referred to in the *EOSC main background documents* prompted an initial list of 566 terms (see [Appendix D: preliminary term list](#)) that has been used as a basis

for determining the different domains and for creating a modular and extensible concept system, that is better suited for the EOSC domain, which is relatively new and rapidly evolving.

In order to release the required intermediate versions of the glossary and to collect early feedback from the community, the development has been structured in macro-phases and iterations based on the domains identified in the preliminary analysis. The methodology followed for each cycle is in line with the aforementioned ISO standards.

The initial phase of the development was influenced by the necessity to analyse and define the EOSC and the MVE in order to contribute to the community discussions. As a consequence a top to bottom approach has been adopted.

The validation has been pursued both during each development cycle and after the release of the results by directly asking feedback to the possible interested parties.

[2, 3] Starting from the *EOSC main background documents*, the official documents, standards and literature have been examined in order to identify the concepts to be included in the glossary and their context of use. The analysed resources, including those suggested by the community, are listed in the appendices [A: EOSC source list](#), [B: terminological data collections](#) and [C: literature](#), for a total of 762 resources.

[4, 7] While already existing authoritative definitions have been reused when possible, new definitions have been created and many existing ones have been modified to assure the coherence and consistency of the glossary. The modifications are indicated in the source section of every glossary entry, which is omitted if a definition has been created ad hoc or if it is the result of significant alteration. The glossary and the definitions are in line with the standards *ISO 704:2009 Terminology work — Principles and methods* and *ISO 10241-1:2011 Terminological entries in standards — Part 1: General requirements and examples of presentation*.

[5] The moderation activities involve the EOSC Glossary Interest Group¹ and the different EOSC glossary releases (see [7] below) which are open for comments and modifications and have been the preferred channel for participating in this co-creation activity.

[6] Because of the difficulties registered in bringing in contributors, rather than organising shared events it has been proved more effective scheduling virtual meetings and sending focused requests to specific groups and persons in parallel with the possibility to openly contribute to the shared documents made public through the EOSC Liaison Platform and the Glossary Interest Group.

[7] Three versions of the Glossary have been released and have been sent to the project manager accompanied by the related report:

1. [EOSC Glossary June 2020](#);

¹ EOSC Glossary Interest Group. <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-glossary>

2. [EOSC Glossary September 2020](#);
3. [EOSC Glossary December 2020](#).

The activities have been carried out in collaboration with and under the supervision of Leonardo Candela who is responsible for the linked co-creation activity #52 - Supervising, monitoring and validating the development of the EOSC Glossary.

Conclusions

The December 2020 version of the glossary consists of 196 concepts, of which 137 are structured and 59 are unstructured or semi-structured (they are structured in a hierarchy outside the main one).

The concept system, which is partitioned into six branches (actor, data, infrastructure, policy, process, service), allows for the understanding of the basic concepts characterising the EOSC domain, although there are branches that still require research, in particular the policy one, and enables further additions and expansions to better follow the constant evolution of the EOSC concepts.

Future activities aiming at strengthening the development and exploitation of the glossary include: (a) the publishing of the Glossary by tools and standards enabling human and machine-actionability, (b) the assignment of persistent and unique identifiers to glossary concepts.

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Appendix A: EOSC source list

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Appendix D: preliminary term list

academic cloud
academic users
Acceptable Use Policies
access
access policy
accessibility
actors
added value services
administration
administrative data
Advisory Board
agencies
aggregated catalogue
architecture
archive services
archiving services
arts objects
Associated Country
Association
Association of participants
attribute sets
attributes
Authentication and Authorisation
Infrastructure
authentication policies
authentication services
authorization policies
authorization services
availability
basic policies
Big Data
bodies
bulk data
business models
business users
calls
career policies
catalogue
certification schemes
citation services
clinical data
clinical trial data
Cloud community
cloud data infrastructures
cloud ecosystem
cloud infrastructure
cloud operations
Cloud providers
cloud service providers
cloud service users
co-funded partnerships
co-programmed partnerships
collaboration
collaboration platform
collection policy
commercial operators
communication
community drivability
community of users
community policies
competition policies
complex data
component
computational infrastructures
compute services
computer centers
computer clusters
computing
computing centres
computing clusters
computing environments
computing infrastructure
computing resources
computing services
confidential data
connectivity infrastructure
consortia
consortium of partners
consumer protection policies
consumers
container platform
content providers
contractual arrangements

contractual Public-Private Partnerships (cPPP)
contributions
cooperation policy
coordination fora
core infrastructure
core PID services
core scientific infrastructure
data
data accessibility policies
data aggregators
data analysis services
data archive services
data archives
data catalogues
data centers
data community
data exchange
data exchange infrastructures
Data generation
data infrastructure
data lifecycle management services
data lifecycle stages
data management
Data management plan
data management policy
data management resources
data management services
data marketplace
data objects
data policy
data preservation
data processing
data producers
data providers
data provision infrastructure
data re-users
data repositories
data resources
Data reuse
data services
data sharing
data sharing policies
data sources

data stewardship
Data storage
data storage infrastructure
data storage resources
data storage services
data storing infrastructures
data user
data-driven science
Data-related policy
Data/Research Initiatives
datasets
Day-to-day operation
decentralization
Digital cultural objects repositories
digital infrastructure
digital library
digital objects
digital platform
digital preservation services
digital research data
digital research resources
digital resource
Digital Service Infrastructure
Director
disciplinary infrastructure
disciplinary research infrastructures
distributed operations
DNS infrastructure
documentation
domain-specific research infrastructures
Domain-user
dynamic data
e-infrastructure
E-infrastructure operators
e-Infrastructure policies
e-infrastructure providers
e-Infrastructure Reflection Group
e-infrastructure resources
e-infrastructure services
e-Science
economic policy
ecosystem
eHealth Digital Service Infrastructure
element

end-users
 entity
 EOSC
 EOSC cluster projects
 EOSC core
 EOSC federating core
 EOSC Minimum Viable Product (MVP)
 EOSC readiness of data
 EOSC-Core
 EOSC-EarthOb
 EOSC-Edu
 EOSC-Exchange
 EU funding Partnership models
 European Data Infrastructure
 European Open Science Cloud
 European Open Science policy
 European Research Area policy
 European Research Infrastructure
 European Research Infrastructure Consortia
 European Strategic Partnerships
 European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
 Evidence-based policy
 Executive Board
 Executive Director
 experimental data
 external users
 extreme data
 FAIR data
 FAIR data infrastructure
 FAIR data policy
 FAIR data principles
 FAIR datasets
 FAIR digital object
 FAIR open data
 FAIR policy
 FAIR research data
 FAIR research data infrastructures
 FAIR services
 FAIR-by-default policies
 FAIR-Data
 federation
 fibre optic infrastructure
 Financial policy
 financing models
 First Iteration
 flexibility
 food data
 foundations
 fraudulent data
 free data
 functionality
 funding agencies
 funding bodies
 funding mechanism
 funding policies
 funding programmes
 General Assembly
 General Assembly of Members
 Geo-spatial data
 governance
 Governance Board
 governance model
 governance scheme
 governance structure
 Governing Board
 governing structure
 government data
 government public data
 grant agreements
 granularity
 hardware resources
 health research data
 help-desk
 High Performance Computing (HPC)
 infrastructure
 high-capacity infrastructures
 High-end users
 High-Performance Computing (HPC)
 resources
 high-speed infrastructure
 High-Throughput Computing (HTC)
 resources
 highly sensitive data
 Horizon Europe
 Horizon Europe policy
 horizontal policy
 hosting organisations

HPC ecosystem	legacy data
HPC infrastructure	legacy research data
HPC resources	legacy science data
HPC services	legal entity
HTC infrastructure	legal vehicle
human infrastructure	Licensing
human resource infrastructure	linked open government data
human users	local users
ICT e-infrastructure	Long-tail users
ICT infrastructure	long-term users
incentive schemes	machine actionable data
inclusiveness	machine readable data
industrial users	machine users
industry users	management policy
infrastructure	marine data
Infrastructure Advisory Group	marketplaces
infrastructure layer	Member States and Associated Countries (MS/AC)
infrastructure of service	membership contracts
infrastructure operators	membership fee structure models
infrastructure policies	membership fees
infrastructure projects	metadata
infrastructure providers	Metadata generation
innovation policy	metadata objects
institutional policies	metadata search service
Institutional Repository	metadata users
institutional users	Minimal Viable EOSC (MVE)
institutionalised partnerships	Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE)
institutions	Minimum Viable Research Data Ecosystem
integrity	ministerial policies
Inter-operable infrastructure services	monetary policy
interlinked data	multidisciplinary data
International European Interest Organisations (IEIOs)	multimedia objects
interoperability	MVE
interoperable data	namespaces
investment policy	network infrastructure
IoT infrastructures	network providers
IT infrastructures	network services
IT platform	networking
journal data policies	networking infrastructures
kernel information	Non-personal data
knowledge transfer policies	NPC operations
landscape	objects
language resources	ocean data

open access data	PID infrastructure
open access platforms	PID issuing
open access policy	PID kernel information
open data	PID linking
open data access policy	PID management
open data infrastructures	PID managers
open data platform	PID metadata
open data policy	PID names
Open Educational Resources (OER)	PID owners
open metrics	PID policy
open platform	PID policy
open research	PID practice
open research data	PID properties
open resources	PID providers
Open Science	PID resolution
open science model	PID schemes
open science platform	PID search
Open Science policy	PID service providers
open source platforms	PID services
openness	PID technical architecture
operation	PID technologies
operator	PID type
organizations	PID user services
Pan-European High Performance	platform
Computing infrastructure	policy
participation	Policy makers
partners	portable infrastructure services
partnership agreements	Portal
partnership funding models	portal operators
partnership implementation modes	portal users
partnership models	portals
partnerships	potential (re)users
persistency	potential user
persistent identifier (PID)	Power-user
persistent identifier (PID) policy	preservability
persistent identifier management policies	pricing policy
persistent identifiers	principle
personal data	private body legal entities
physical infrastructure	private companies
PID attribute sets	private sector users
PID authorities	private users
PID ecosystem	production operation
PID governance	profiles
PID graph	Programme Committee(s)

project users
provider
public data
public policies
public research data
public users
public-public partnerships
publication platforms
publications policies
publishing platforms
quality assurance conditions
R&I policies
raw data
RDM Policies
real-time data
referent
Registry of Data
reliability
replicability
reporting schemes
repositories
research communities
Research Communities and Institutions
research community
research data
research data infrastructure
research data management policies
research data management services
research data networks
research data repositories
research data services
research e-infrastructures
research ecosystem
research entities
research facilities
research funders
research information ecosystem
Research information management systems
research information objects
research information systems
research infrastructure
research infrastructure ecosystem
research infrastructure policy
research institutions
research integrity policy
research laboratories
research orientation
research platform
research policy
research products
research resources
research sector users
research support policies
research users
research workflow system
researchers
resolvability
resource aggregator
resource operator
resource providers
resources
Responsible Research and Innovation
policy (RRI)
reusability
reusable data
revenues
reviews
rich data
rules
Rules of Participation
scalability
scholarly infrastructure
science infrastructure
science policies
science policy
science users
scientific cloud infrastructure
scientific data
scientific data infrastructure
scientific domain-users
scientific infrastructures
scientific resources
scientific user
Second iteration
sensitive data
service
service aggregators
service catalog

Service Catalogues
Service Definitions
service developer
service frameworks
Service Level Agreements
Service Level Specification
service marketplace
service maturity level
service operators
service policies
service providers
service users
services
simulation data
small data
SMEs (Small or Medium Enterprises)
SMEs users
social infrastructure
software infrastructure
stability
stakeholder
stakeholder organizations
Stakeholders Forum
statutes
stewards
storage resources
strategic research policies
supercomputer resources
supercomputing infrastructure
support policy
sustainability
syntax
technical infrastructure
technical platform
technology independence
technology policies
Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
Terms and Conditions
thematic data infrastructures
third iteration
third party users
trade policy
training
training infrastructure
transparency
transparent operations
uniqueness
universities
users
values
versioning
visibility
work programmes